

Syllabus Introduction to in silico medicine for non-engineers with a focus on bioinformatics

1. Introduction

The learning goals indicate the requirements of each lecture of the course 'Introduction to in silico medicine for non-engineers with a focus on bioinformatics' (6 ECTS). Based on these requirements the instructors can format their lecture based on their own teaching preferences, knowledge and experience, while ensuring a qualitative introductory course on in silico medicine. Note that some learning goals are formulated for more than one lecture. This does not mean that the learning goals should be achieved in each of these lectures. It is the aim that the learning goals are achieved in at least one of the lectures, but how they are distributed over the lectures is up to the preferences of the instructor.

2. Overview lectures and exercise sessions

Week	Lecture (2h)	Topic lecture	Exercise session (4h)	Topic exercise session
1	L01	Introduction to bioinformatics - Part I	P01	Introduction to bioinformatics - Part I
2	L02	Introduction to bioinformatics - Part II	P02	Introduction to bioinformatics - Part II
3	L03	Introduction to bioengineering - Part I	P03	Introduction to bioengineering - Part I
4	L04	Introduction to bioengineering - Part II	P04	Introduction to bioengineering - Part II
5	L05	Introduction to in silico medicine: can nature be predicted?	P05	Introduction to in silico medicine: can nature be predicted?
6	L06	From a clinical problem to a digital twin in healthcare	P06	From a clinical problem to a digital twin in healthcare
7	L07	Examples of in silico medicine: replacement of in vitro, animal and human experimentation - Part I	P07	Examples of in silico medicine: replacement of in vitro, animal and human experimentation - Part I
8	L08	Examples of in silico medicine: replacement of in vitro, animal and human experimentation - Part II	P08	Examples of in silico medicine: replacement of in vitro, animal and human experimentation - Part II
9	L09	In silico trials for medical devices	P09	In silico trials for medical devices
10	L10	In silico trials for medicinal devices	P10	In silico trials for medicinal devices
11	L11	In silico medicine: ethical and social considerations	P11	In silico medicine: ethical and social considerations
12	L12	Communication in interdisciplinary settings	P12	Communication in interdisciplinary settings

3. Lectures

L01: Introduction to bioinformatics - Part I

Applicable ILOs

H1.5.1: Program algorithms using interpreted programming languages and specialised libraries (Python, R, Matlab)

H1.5.4: Program algorithms for bioinformatics (sequence analysis, expression analysis, structural analysis, network analysis)

Learning goals

- *Develop algorithms to analyse and visualize biological data using Python, R and Matlab;*
- *Illustrate the use of sequence, expression, structural as well as network analysis in the medical field with state-of-the-art examples;*
- *Identify and clarify the global structure of an algorithm that is able to perform sequence, expression, structural or network analysis;*
- *Implement algorithms that are able to perform sequence, expression, structural or network analysis for simple case studies.*

L02: Introduction to bioinformatics - Part II

Applicable ILOs

H1.5.1: Program algorithms using interpreted programming languages and specialised libraries (Python, R, Matlab)

H1.5.4: Program algorithms for bioinformatics (sequence analysis, expression analysis, structural analysis, network analysis)

Learning goals

- *Develop algorithms to analyse and visualize biological data using Python, R and Matlab;*
- *Illustrate the use of sequence, expression, structural as well as network analysis in the medical field with state-of-the-art examples;*
- *Identify and clarify the global structure of an algorithm that is able to perform sequence, expression, structural or network analysis;*
- *Implement algorithms that are able to perform sequence, expression, structural or network analysis for simple case studies.*

L03: Introduction to bioengineering - Part I

Applicable ILOs

H1.4.1: Select appropriate biomedical instrumentation to obtain the desired information

H1.4.2: Select appropriate medical imaging instrumentation to obtain the desired information

H1.4.3: Select appropriate in vitro diagnostics instrumentation to obtain the desired information

H1.4.4: Elaborate bio-signals and medical images

Learning goals

- *Explain the working principles of biomedical instrumentation that is commonly used in the clinical practice;*
- *Identify appropriate biomedical instrumentation to collect the required data for a given example case and explain its global working principle;*
- *Explain the working principles of clinically used medical imaging techniques, such as computed tomography, magnetic resonance imaging and ultrasound;*
- *Identify appropriate medical imaging instrumentation to collect the required data for a given example case;*
- *Explain the working principles of in vitro diagnostics instrumentation that is commonly used in clinical laboratories;*
- *Identify appropriate in vitro diagnostic instrumentation to collect the required data for a given example case.*

L04: Introduction to bioengineering - Part II

Applicable ILOs

H1.4.1: Select appropriate biomedical instrumentation to obtain the desired information

H1.4.2: Select appropriate medical imaging instrumentation to obtain the desired information

H1.4.3: Select appropriate in vitro diagnostics instrumentation to obtain the desired information

H1.4.4: Elaborate bio-signals and medical images

Learning goals

- *Explain the working principles of biomedical instrumentation that is commonly used in the clinical practice;*
- *Identify appropriate biomedical instrumentation to collect the required data for a given example case and explain its global working principle;*
- *Explain the working principles of clinically used medical imaging techniques, such as computed tomography, magnetic resonance imaging and ultrasound;*

- *Identify appropriate medical imaging instrumentation to collect the required data for a given example case;*
- *Explain the working principles of in vitro diagnostics instrumentation that is commonly used in clinical laboratories;*
- *Identify appropriate in vitro diagnostic instrumentation to collect the required data for a given example case.*

L05: Introduction to in silico medicine: can nature be predicted?

Applicable ILOs

NA

Learning goals

- *Understand the complexity of dealing with predictions about human health;*
- *Identify the origins of barriers against adoption of in silico technologies (complexity, redundancy, stochasticity, culture);*
- *Summarize first examples of digital twins and in silico trials developed;*
- *Assess the value of the in silico trials in the development of new medical products;*
- *Outline the 3R concept that led in silico trials;*
- *Illustrate how in silico technologies might be of help to ensure and extend the healthcare, given how the world population is growing;*
- *Explain what the virtual human twin will be.*

L06: From a clinical problem to a digital twin in healthcare

Applicable ILOs

H2.1: Extract key concepts from briefings provided by experts of in silico methodologies

Learning goals

- *Formulate a definition of a digital twin in healthcare;*
- *Summarize the potential benefits of using a digital twin in healthcare;*
- *Clarify the main challenges to integrate in silico medicine in the current clinical practice;*
- *Identify the subsequent steps of the workflow that translates a clinical problem to a digital twin;*
- *Give two examples of existing clinical problems that could benefit from in silico medicine.*

L07: Examples of in silico medicine: replacement of in vitro, animal and human experimentation - Part I

Applicable ILOs

H4.1: Evaluate the unmet need in terms of reduction, refinement, or replacement of in vitro, animal, or human experimentation

Learning goals

- *Give three examples of in silico medicine that have been used to replace and/or refine in vitro, animal and human experimentation;*
- *Discuss the advantages and disadvantages of replacing and/or refining in vitro, animal and human experiments by in silico medicine;*
- *Identify how in silico medicine can be applied to replace and/or refine in vitro, animal and/or human experimentation for a given case study;*
- *Discuss how the credibility of an in silico model can be assessed.*

L08: Examples of in silico medicine: replacement of in vitro, animal and human experimentation - Part II

Applicable ILOs

H4.1: Evaluate the unmet need in terms of reduction, refinement, or replacement of in vitro, animal, or human experimentation

Learning goals

- *Give three examples of in silico medicine that have been used to replace and/or refine in vitro, animal and human experimentation;*
- *Discuss the advantages and disadvantages of replacing and/or refining in vitro, animal and human experiments by in silico medicine;*
- *Identify how in silico medicine can be applied to replace and/or refine in vitro, animal and/or human experimentation for a given case study.*
- *Discuss how the credibility of an in silico model can be assessed.*

L09: In silico trials for medical devices

Applicable ILOs

H4.14: Use in silico methodologies to discover, develop/design, evaluate the safety and the efficacy, evaluate the cost-effectiveness of new candidate diagnostics or new interventions

Learning goals

- *Formulate a definition of medical devices in the context of in silico medicine;*
- *Outline a typical workflow for the development of in silico trials for medical devices;*
- *Give two examples of in silico trials for medical devices;*
- *Critically reflect on the limitations of a given case study of an in silico trial for medical devices;*
- *Showcase how in silico methods can contribute in different phases of the development process of medical devices.*

L10: In silico trials for medicinal products

Applicable ILOs

H4.14: Use in silico methodologies to discover, develop/design, evaluate the safety and the efficacy, evaluate the cost-effectiveness of new candidate diagnostics or new interventions

Learning goals

- *Formulate a definition of medicinal products in the context of in silico medicine;*
- *Distinguish between in silico trial for medical devices and medicinal products;*
- *Outline a typical workflow for the development of in silico trials for medicinal products;*
- *Give two examples of in silico trials for medicinal products;*
- *Critically reflect on a given case study of an in silico trial for medicinal products in relation to the regulatory and ethical consideration;*
- *Showcase how in silico methods can contribute in different phases of the development process of medicinal products.*

L11: In silico medicine: ethical and social considerations

Applicable ILOs

H2.5: Collect and use key concepts on ethical risks and opportunities of in silico methodologies in communication

H2.6: Collect and use key concepts on social risks and opportunities of in silico methodologies to the public and patients

Learning goals

- *Write down an overview of the most important ethical risks that need to be accounted for when developing an in silico methodology;*
- *Critically discuss the benefits and drawbacks of the use of in silico medicine from an ethical perspective and illustrate with example cases;*
- *Write down an overview of the most important social risks that need to be accounted for when developing an in silico methodology;*
- *Critically discuss the benefits and drawbacks of the use of in silico medicine from a social perspective and illustrate with example cases.*

L12: Communication in interdisciplinary settings

Applicable ILOs

H2.2: Collect and use key concepts and definitions related to in silico methodologies in communication

Learning goals

- *Explain technical terms such as segmentation, registration, meshing and in silico modeling in layman's terms;*
- *Identify how in silico models can contribute to a given clinical need;*
- *Formulate the benefits and drawbacks of an in silico model based on communication with healthcare professionals.*

4. Exercise sessions

The learning goals indicated in grey correspond to learning goals that have also been formulated for the lectures. By pursuing the same learning goal in a different context (e.g. understanding an example during the lecture and applying a concept during the exercise session), a better understanding of the considered aspect is expected.

P01: Relevant software tools - Part I

Description

Student follow tutorials of the different types of software that they will need in the development of in silico model.

For example: segmentation software, meshing software, finite element software, computational fluid dynamics software, ABM software, etc.

Learning goals

- *Reproduce the steps presented by a tutorial in order to develop a prescribed model in the in silico software;*
- *Formulate which algorithms are used by the applied software to calculate the result;*
- *Explain the meaning and functionality of each step needed to develop the in silico model;*
- *Summarize the subsequent steps needed to develop the in silico model.*

P02: Relevant software tools - Part II

Description

Student follow tutorials of the different types of software that they will need in the development of in silico model.

For example: segmentation software, meshing software, finite element software, computational fluid dynamics software, ABM software, etc.

It is recommended that a different type of software is considered compared to PO1, to allow the students to get acquainted to a variety of in silico software tools.

Learning goals

- *Reproduce the steps presented by a tutorial in order to develop a prescribed model in the in silico software;*
- *Formulate which algorithms are used by the applied software to calculate the result;*
- *Explain the meaning and functionality of each step needed to develop the in silico model;*
- *Summarize the subsequent steps needed to develop the in silico model.*

P03: Introduction to bioinformatics - Part I

Description

The students receive assignments in which they have to visualize given datasets, related to a medical/clinical problem, to explore the data using Python, R or Matlab. Afterwards, the students further analyse the given datasets by implementing the algorithms needed to answer the questions. In the second part of the session, the students implement sequence, expression, structural or network analysis algorithms for strongly simplified case studies. The focus is situated on getting acquainted with the algorithms and their implementation.

Learning goals

- *Develop algorithms to analyse and visualize biological data using Python, R and Matlab;*
- *Implement algorithms that are able to perform sequence, expression, structural or network analysis for simple case studies.*

P04: Introduction to bioinformatics - Part II

Description

The students implement sequence, expression, structural or network analysis algorithms for more realistic case studies. The focus is situated on the application of the algorithms in a more complex and realistic context.

Learning goals

- *Develop algorithms to analyse and visualize biological data using Python, R and Matlab;*
- *Implement algorithms that are able to perform sequence, expression, structural or network analysis for more advanced case studies.*

P05: Introduction to bioengineering

Description

Rather than a classical exercise session, a more practically hands-on session in which the students can familiarize themselves with the biomedical and in vitro diagnostics instrumentation is strongly recommended. The students get the opportunity to see some of the instruments discussed during the lecture in real-life. In the first part of the session, the students get a demo of the different instruments and a recap of their general working principles, input and output. Afterwards, the students are divided into groups and each group goes along all different biomedical instruments to gain some hands-on experience with the instrumentation (if possible). In the last part of the session, the students receive some assignments related to the basic data processing of imaging data.

Learning goals

- *Identify appropriate biomedical instrumentation to collect the required data for a given example case and explain its global working principle;*
- *Identify appropriate in vitro diagnostic instrumentation to collect the required data for a given example case;*
- *Perform basic operations on some biomedical and in vitro diagnostics instrumentation.*
- *Implement basic operations for the processing of imaging data.*

P06: From a clinical problem to a digital twin in healthcare

Description

Based on a case study from the clinical practice, preferably presented by the surgeon/clinician, the students determine the requirements and specifications for a digital twin. Afterwards, they develop a workflow to translate the clinical problem a digital twin (without really creating the digital twin themselves). The student critically discuss the benefits and challenges related to the use of the suggested digital twin in the clinical practice.

Learning goals

- *Summarize the potential benefits of using a digital twin in healthcare;*
- *Clarify the main challenges to integrate in silico medicine in the current clinical practice related to a specific case study;*
- *Identify the subsequent steps of the workflow that translates a clinical problem to a digital twin;*
- *Determine the global requirements and specifications for a digital twin based on a clinical case study.*

P07: Development of an in silico model as replacement of in vitro and animal experimentation

Description

The students develop an in silico model aimed at replacing a given animal or in vitro experiment. Based on a given geometry, the students determine the relevant boundary and loading conditions and use proper software tools to develop the model.

Learning goals

- *Identify how in silico medicine can be applied to replace in vitro or animal experimentation for a given case study.*
- *Discuss how the credibility of an in silico model can be assessed;*
- *Implement an in silico model to serve as replacement of a given in vitro or animal experiment with state-of-the-art software tools.*
- *Formulate proper boundary and loading conditions for an in silico model that serves as replacement of a given in vitro or animal experiment.*

- *Design a proper geometry for an in silico model that serves as replacement of a given in vitro or animal experiment.*

P08: Development of an in silico model as replacement of human experimentation

Description

The students develop an in silico model aimed at refining a given human experiment. Based on a given geometry, the students determine the relevant boundary and loading conditions and use proper software tools to develop the model.

Learning goals

- *Identify how in silico medicine can be applied to refine human experimentation for a given case study.*
- *Discuss how the credibility of an in silico model can be assessed;*
- *Implement an in silico model to contribute to the refinement of a given human experiment with state-of-the-art software tools.*
- *Formulate proper boundary and loading conditions for an in silico model that contributes in the refinement of a given human experiment.*
- *Design a proper geometry for an in silico model that contributes in the refinement of a given human experiment.*

P09: In silico trials for medical devices

Description

The students develop an in silico trial for a given case study on a medical device with defined specifications. In the development process, the students situate the in silico trial in the development process of the medical device, determine the aim of the in silico trial, the available input and the desired output and create the in silico model with available software tools. The students also reflect on how the credibility of the developed in silico model and the corresponding in silico trial could be assessed.

Learning goals

- *Outline a typical workflow for the development of in silico trials for medical devices;*
- *Critically reflect on the limitations of a given case study of an in silico trial for medical devices;*
- *Showcase how in silico methods can contribute in different phases of the development process of medical devices.*
- *Implement an in silico model used in an in silico trial for a medical device with state-of-the-art software tools.*
- *Formulate proper boundary and loading conditions for an in silico model used in an in silico trial for a medical device.*

- *Design a proper geometry for an in silico model used in an in silico trial for a medical device;*
- *Discuss how the credibility of the developed in silico model can be assessed.*

P10: In silico trials for medicinal devices

Description

The students develop an in silico trial for a given case study on a medicinal product with defined specifications. In the development process, the students situate the in silico trial in the development process of the medicinal product, determine the aim of the in silico trial, the available input and the desired output and create the in silico model with available software tools. The students also reflect on how the credibility of the developed in silico model and the corresponding in silico trial could be assessed.

Learning goals

- *Outline a typical workflow for the development of in silico trials for medicinal products;*
- *Critically reflect on the limitations of a given case study of an in silico trial for medicinal products;*
- *Showcase how in silico methods can contribute in different phases of the development process of medicinal products.*
- *Implement an in silico model used in an in silico trial for a medicinal product with state-of-the-art software tools.*
- *Formulate proper boundary and loading conditions for an in silico model used in an in silico trial for a medicinal product.*
- *Design a proper geometry for an in silico model used in an in silico trial for a medicinal product;*
- *Discuss how the credibility of the developed in silico model can be assessed.*

P11: In silico trials - part II with inclusion of ethical and social considerations

Description

The students choose one of the in silico trials they developed during P09 and P10. They continue the development of that model. Besides, they consider and discuss the model from an ethical and social perspective.

Learning goals

- *Outline a typical workflow for the development of in silico trials for medical devices/medicinal products;*
- *Showcase how in silico methods can contribute in different phases of the development process of medical devices/medicinal products;*
- *Implement an in silico model used in an in silico trial for a medical device with state-of-the-art software tools;*

- *Formulate proper boundary and loading conditions for an in silico model used in an in silico trial for a medical device;*
- *Design a proper geometry for an in silico model used in an in silico trial for a medical device;*
- *Critically reflect on a given case study of an in silico trial for medical devices/medicinal products in relation to the ethical and social considerations;*
- *Discuss how the credibility of an in silico model can be assessed.*

P12: Communication on in silico medicine

Description

Students present the developed in silico trial of their choice (for a medical device or a medicinal product) to an interdisciplinary audience. The presentation includes a short discussion on the ethical and social considerations of the developed model. Students follow the presentation and summarize three presentations of fellow-students in max. 10 lines, by extracting the most essential aspects of each presentation.

Learning goals

- *Explain technical terms such as segmentation, registration, meshing and in silico modeling in layman's terms;*
- *Explain credibility terms such as verification, validation and uncertainty quantification in layman's terms;*
- *Identify how in silico models can contribute to a given clinical need.*